

DTERBIM News

Insights on digital, circular and energy-efficient construction and renovation

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Dear reader,

In this edition, we spotlight the women driving innovation at DTERBIM, share key project updates, explore how our pilots are bringing digital and circular renovation into practice, and share key opportunities, resources, and insights from across the construction and renovation sector.

Let's get started!

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Main story:

Celebrating the women driving innovation in DTERBIM

International Women's Day 2026

**Building the future:
celebrating the women
driving innovation in DTERBIM**

Did you know that women represent only 10% of Europe’s construction workforce, 34% of STEM graduates, and 22% of AI professionals? These aren’t just statistics. They represent perspectives we cannot afford to miss.

On International Women’s Day 2026, we spotlighted **six women from the DTERBIM team** who are **helping shape the future of digital and circular construction**. We spoke with them about their career journeys, what motivates them, and their advice for the next generation.

Their stories show that **diverse perspectives are essential to building more sustainable, collaborative construction ecosystems**.

“I clearly remember my first European projects. There might have been only one or two women. Over time, however, I have seen positive change.” — Ane Ferreiro Sistiaga, CYPE

“Our multidisciplinary team reflects this evolution, combining architecture, engineering, BIM, and AI.” — Sonia Álvarez, CARTIF

“Never underestimate your abilities. Stay curious and surround yourself with people who support your growth.” — Gloria Calleja-Rodríguez, CEMOSA

[Read the full article](#)

A key milestone: Tools & Services Workshop

TOOL NAME Construction Digital Twin (CDT) for planning, progress monitoring & quality control

PARTNERS UCL, NOW, CEM, CIB, ACC, FAS, WET, RPH, ISP

WORK PACKAGE WP4

TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS

Main objective of the tool

Create a dynamic, digital replica of the construction project by combining 4D BIM with real-time site data, to continuously track planned vs. actual progress and support quality control decisions.

Main benefits for the user

Support several applications:
(1) a mobile app by CCM for digitizing and automating on-site data collection;
(2) the CON 4D Planner app for simulating 4D models to track construction progress; and
(3) integration with tools like Data and Autodesk BIM 360 for quality management through digital checklists, issue tracking, and BIM integration.

Real-time visibility of construction status vs plans; fewer manual site checks and less rework; better coordination with subcontractors; evidence-based quality assurance; improved as-built documentation and traceability.

Stakeholders involved

Construction managers / planners
Site engineers / supervisors
Quality managers / inspectors
BIM/VDC managers
Owners & general contractors

Quality managers / inspectors
BIM/VDC managers

DTERRBIM Co-funded by the European Union

We recently reviewed the full suite of DTERBIM tools and services across all building lifecycle stages and started defining the use cases that will guide the upcoming validation phase.

This work will shape how our tools are developed, tested, and refined in the coming months.

The session was a great opportunity to align across partners and connect technical development with real renovation needs.

[Learn more](#) →

DTERBIM featured in Materiały Budowlane

We are proud to appear on the cover of the December 2025 issue of the prestigious Materiały Budowlane journal!

This special edition celebrates the 200th anniversary of the Faculty of Civil Engineering at the Warsaw University of Technology, one of [DTERBIM's pilot sites in Poland](#).

The cover showcases a 3D mesh generated from a point cloud of the Faculty building.

[Learn more](#) →

New resource: DTERBIM's Brand Book

The DTERBIM Brand Book is a practical guide to our identity, outlining key messages, target audiences, tone of voice, and visual guidelines to ensure clear, consistent communication.

[Learn more](#) →

The DTERBIM pilots

At DTERBIM, we go beyond theory. We are validating our BIM-based process, toolkit, and openBIM framework through a combination of virtual and real-life pilots across Europe.

Virtual pilots: Testing technologies at early stages to ensure readiness, interoperability, and robustness.

Real-life pilots

- Residential historical building in Valladolid
- Academic building and offices in Warsaw
- Kindergarten and elementary school in Athens

Across all pilots, we explore how digital tools, AI services, and interoperable data can optimise resources, reduce time and costs, and embed circularity throughout the building lifecycle.

[Learn more](#) →

Fresh news from the sector

Event: [BIM World MUNICH 2026](#)
(24-25 Nov)

Thought leaders and professionals will explore digital twin workflows across design, construction, and operations, including how real-time analytics and sensor data improve collaboration and lifecycle outcomes.

Research article: [Explainable digital twins for circular construction: A systematic review of real-time decision-making and urban retrofitting frameworks](#)

A recent peer-reviewed journal article explores how Digital Twins, when integrated with explainable AI and circular construction principles, can improve real-time decision-making, lifecycle reuse, and transparency in infrastructure workflows.

Podcast episode: [Reality Capture 101: Laser Scanning, BIM, and Digital Twins](#)

In this episode of the Digital Construction Podcast, expert Michael Alder discusses laser scanning, reality capture, BIM, and Digital Twins, and how they contribute to improved coordination, accuracy, and collaboration across project phases.

Journal paper: [Human centric digital twins for sustainable supply chain in construction](#)

This open-access article discusses digital twin applications within construction supply chains, emphasising stakeholder collaboration, sustainability, and lifecycle management.

Thank you for being part of the DTERBIM community and following our journey.

Let's continue driving digital and circular renovation together!

The DTERBIM Team

Get in touch

Your feedback is a gift to us!

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